

Artificial Intelligence in Computational Mechanics and Biomechanics

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Abstract

This work aims to deliver a brief presentation and evolution of Artificial intelligence (AI) and its potentially most suited methodologies for Computational Mechanics and Biomechanics (CM&B) applications, such as Machine Learning (ML), Pattern Recognition (PR), Deep Learning (DL) and DL using artificial Neural Networks (NN). Afterwards, since DL using artificial NN is the AI methodology mostly used in CM&B, this methodology applied to CM&B problems is described with more detail. In order to show the evolution of AI methodologies in CM&B, a large document search was performed in the academic database Web of Science. Thus, peer-reviewed relevant articles addressing the topics of ML, PR, DL and NN combined with CMB&B were selected for a quantitative analysis. The results confirm that DL using artificial NN is in fact the most used AI methodology in both CM&B. Furthermore, it was found that research using DL using artificial NN combined with the finite element method is growing much faster than any other methodology combination. This work shows the inevitable growth of AI, which will accelerate the computation of today's demanding problems and will allow the simulation of highly complex problems beyond the competence of existing rigid computational methodologies. AI offers the opportunity to expand the traditional application fields of CM&B, which will change its paradigm in a very near future.

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1 Introduction

To this day, Computational Mechanics and Biomechanics (CM&B) were supported by well-established computer science branches, such as: mathematical foundations; algorithms and data structures; computer graphics; concurrent, parallel and distributed systems; programming languages and compilers; scientific computing; software engineering; and theory of computation. However, modern CM&B interest fields started to become much more complex and challenging than traditional research areas, and standard computational techniques became insufficient to answer to such demanding problems. Thus, very recently, computational mechanics has started to interact with another fields of computer science, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and analytical databases [1,2].

AI, formally introduced in 1956 by Russell et al. [3], is a vast computer science branch, possessing specific research techniques and terminology depending on the research topic. The core techniques of AI have the potential to radically change the biomechanical and structural modelling and programming as we know it. High-level AI techniques and programming are capable to implement advanced methodologies to develop, enhance and apply new numerical methods that defy human comprehension, allowing to achieve more efficient computational mechanics algorithms/codes and more realistic multiscale material constitutive laws. In order to solve engineering problems, AI attempts to capture the principle of human cognition by means of symbol manipulation and symbolically structured knowledge. However, in contradiction, AI solutions frequently defy traditional and analytical methodologies under human linear comprehension.

Today, AI is widely spread by many science fields and several terms also denoting AI are mentioned in the literature, which can cause confusion [1]. Two very close terms are machine intelligence [4] and cognitive computing [5]. Although sometimes used a synonyms, MI and AI are actually distinct concepts. Machine Intelligence (MI) deals with machines with human-like reasoning and behaviour. On the other hand, AI deals with algorithms attempting to reproduce the human reasoning and intelligent behaviour. AI tries to replicate the human cognitive functions and performing the same tasks faster and more accurately. Cognitive Computing (CC), associated with the competences of the human mind, refers to the in-silico replication of human reasoning. CC is a highly challenging field, focusing in the development of algorithms capable of recognizing patterns, training and learning and interpreting big data. In opposition to AI, which

requires an (internal or external) entity deciding which actions are to be taken during the training process, CC is capable to learn, reason and interact as/with a human [1].

With the increase of the available computational power, the general scientific community started to focus in AI. Engineering is no exception. The partnership between CM&B with AI is still in its infancy. However, even today, it is possible to predict and visualize several challenging and promising research fields combining this exciting computation science branch with innovative CM&B approaches. Although AI possesses several methodologies, this work will focus only in four AI techniques presenting a strong potential in CM&B: Machine Learning (ML), Pattern Recognition (PR), Deep Learning (DL) and DL using artificial Neural Networks (NN). Although DP can include propositional formulas or latent variables architectures, most modern DP models are based on artificial NN architectures. Thus, the NN term is frequently used as a substitute term for DL.

2 Artificial Intelligence

It is possible to classify machine intelligence as hard computing or soft computing techniques [1]. Hard computing is the most used in CB&B, it is based in numerical analysis, binary and Boolean logic. Requiring analytical models and rigid and well-defined formulations, hard computing is capable to deliver accurate, robust and repeatable solutions. In this conventional and deterministic computing, the programming code is written, which always provides the same output field solution for the same input variables. In opposition, by including stochastic formulations, parallelization and handling noisy and ambiguous data, soft computing is capable to autonomously develop further its own algorithms and deliver approximate solutions in a fraction of time. Generally, when compared with hard computing, soft computing is less accurate, however it is much faster. Some authors use the term Computational Intelligence (CI) instead soft computing [6]. In order to provide solutions for highly complex problems, CI combines probabilistic methods, fuzzy logic, evolutionary computing, artificial neural networks and learning theory. Most of the problems in biomechanics and micro-mechanics involve numerous input variables, most of which are stochastically uncertain or unobservable. Such difficulty, associated with the process complexity, hinders the use or the development of accurate/useful mathematical models. By means of sample data or experimental observation, CI allows to develop new nonlinear rules approximating a solution using nature-inspired computational techniques [7]. Although their definitions overlap, today it is establish that CI is one of the many subsets of AI [8]. Another two relevant subsets of AI are data science and data mining. Data science/mining uses data to disclose trends, which can then allow to understand complex phenomena and provide much accurate predictions than incomplete or approximated formulations from hard computing. If the data used in data science/mining is large in volume, frequency and diversity, such data is denoted as “big data”. Notice that the volume of the data is related with the number of data points (the observable results), the frequency is associated with the number of data acquired per unit of time and the diversity is related with the distinct types of data acquired (material distribution, volume fraction, species, etc.). Due to the large volume, frequency and diversity of these data sets, the data processing techniques traditionally used in hard computing are not capable to interpret or represent big data. As already mentioned, machine learning is an AI methodology. ML uses training data to learn and develop models which are capable to deliver trends and predictions. Deep learning, as a subset of ML, was developed to analyse big data and identify trends and classify data into categories. Fig.1(a) represents the connection between AI methodologies.

Fig.1 - (a) Schematic representation of the connection between AI methodologies; (b) Feed forward neural network consisting of one input layer, several hidden layers, one output layer. Each layer containing one or more units.

In fact, in CM&B the problem solution strongly depends on decisions, such as the problem domain (scale, size, dimension, geometry, etc.), the boundary conditions (initial imposed variable fields, variable constrains, etc.), the material uncertainties (mechanical properties, heterogeneity, anisotropy, constitutive model, etc.) methodology

(continuous methods, discrete techniques, machine precision, etc.) and the formulation (elastic, hyperelastic, elastoplastic, damage mechanics, fracture mechanics, heat-transfer, fluid mechanics, etc.). These decisions are made by humans, and the solution's accuracy is highly influenced by the experience and knowledge of the researcher/engineer. Most of these decisions could be done by AI techniques, such as selecting the most accurate number of integration points per integration cell in a finite element analysis [2]. Due to the unique character of the problems involved in CM&B, hard computation is still its mainstream process. Past experience can be encoded and turned into big data, which can then be analysed and converted into trends and AI rules. AI methodologies are becoming increasingly useful, as shown by the CM&B applications combined with deep learning and model order reduction [9] or multiscale homogenization techniques [10].

3 Deep learning and Neural Networks in CM&B

The AI, using artificial NN, the core technique of DL, has already been tested and applied in relevant computational mechanics fields [2,11]. Artificial NN can be classified by their architectural structure as “feed forward neural networks” or “mutually connected neural networks”. In Fig.1(b) is shown a schematic representation of a feed forward neural network. As shown in the extensive review in [2], since artificial NN are capable of nonlinear mapping, NN are suitable to estimate crack growth [12], enhance contact algorithms [13] and improve the nonlinear solution methods [14] and variational formulations [15], among many other applications.

In fact, for complex problems, artificial NN require long training, demand a high computational cost, and present a low convergence. One possible solution is to simplify the problem. Therefore, until now, the majority of the artificial NN implemented in computational mechanics used simple and reduced amount of learning patterns and epochs. Thus, the simulated mapping of those applications is basic and its solutions space is narrowed. Fortunately, in the last few years, computational power and processor architectures have improved significantly and training algorithms for artificial NN have been enhanced considerably. This combined events allow to train large NN, entering the DL field. Thus, artificial NN with DL have become accessible to study much more complex problems within the CM&B fields.

In standard CM&B, first, it is necessary to identify or develop the partial differential equation ruling the physical or biological phenomena under study. Then, combining it with a discretization technique, the system of equations is established and, after setting the essential and natural boundary conditions, the system of equations is solved numerically. All the steps and rules for solving the process were developed by human and all decisions are human dependent. It was the human observation of physical or biological phenomena, combined with its mathematical comprehension, that allowed to develop the partial differential equations and constitutive material laws available in the literature. All the rules developed by humans are limited by human's natural perception, intellectual capacity and acquired awareness.

AI permits to expand and amplify human's intelligence. For instances, ML using DL and artificial NN allowed to process large amount of random and unstructured data, offering the possibility to discover automatically new rules. Regarding the ability to find and develop new rules, the literature shows that, among ML methods, DL is superior to any other technique [2]. Using large data sets, DL is capable to discover rules that are too much complex to be understood by human's comprehension. DL rules are not explicit rules, mathematical equations or structured algorithms, possessing explicit symbolic representations within human's cognitive bound. DL rules are represented by implicit mapping, being flexible enough to adapt to new training data or human's input. When compared with explicit rules, DL is capable to handle with higher efficiency the complex relation between the several variables and parameters involved in the observed phenomenon. Thus, DL is able to develop the mapping associating those variables and parameters and, at the same time, update and evolve the mapping with new data. In order to implement DL with artificial NN in CM&B, the following phases can be generically followed [2].

Data preparation phase: an input-output association is established, being the input represented by the n -dimensional vector $\Psi = \{\psi_1^p, \psi_2^p, \dots, \psi_n^p\}$ and the output represented by the m -dimensional vector $\Phi = \{\phi_1^p, \phi_2^p, \dots, \phi_m^p\}$. Each component of vectors Ψ and Φ can be an integer or real number. The superscript p indicates the p^{th} data pairs of a large data set of pair. It is recommended to gather and use a representative number of data pairs in order to efficiently establish the mapping relation between them. Such massive gathering can be achieved using CM&B analyses.

Training phase: in this phase DL starts the training aiming to achieve the mapping rules governing the input-output data pairs gathered in the data preparation phase. Thus, an artificial NN considers the n -dimensional input-data contained in Ψ as the input to the NN and, as corresponding teacher signal, the artificial NN considers the m -dimensional vector $\Phi = \{\phi_1^p, \phi_2^p, \dots, \phi_m^p\}$. Errors and deviations are calculated between the input and the output towards convergence.

When convergence is achieved, multi-dimensional mapping is attained: $\mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$, allowing to establish an input-output relation: $\Phi = f(\Psi)$, being f the implicit mapping function.

Application phase: the input-output relationship is no longer obtained with explicit formulations, as the ones applied in the data preparation phase. In the application phase the output data is approximated with the mapping function obtained by DL in the training phase. The trained artificial NN, whose training allowed to achieve the implicit mapping function, can be retrained with additional data pairs, generated and gathered from additional CM&B simulations or even from other sources, such as experimental trials. Expletively, relevant supplementary data pairs will allow to enhance the artificial NN and enhance the efficiency and accuracy of the prediction.

4 Literature evolution

This section evaluates the available literature, collecting data from the academic database Web of Science. Peer-reviewed relevant articles were selected for the quantitative analysis presented here. The search in the database was performed using representative keyword combinations, indicated in Table 1, and selecting the “topic/scope” (TS) field in the advanced search. Table 1 shows both the acronyms from the keyword combination and the corresponding total number of papers found for each keyword combination. The acronyms identified in Table 1 for each of the keyword combination are the ones used to refer the corresponding results within Fig.2. The literature search provided a general vision of AI applications in CM&B. From Table 1, it is possible to observe a reduced number of papers combining AI methodologies with CM&B. On the other hand, the combination of FEM with AI methodologies is more relevant, mostly FEM combined with NN.

Fig.2(a) shows the number of papers published per year using the keywords TS-AI, TS-ML, TS-PR, TS-DP, TS-NN and “Finite Element Method” (TS-FEM). This search is independent of the application field. It is not narrowed to CM&B applications. FEM is the most popular discrete numerical method used in CMB&B, therefore, it is relevant to compare the evolution of the number of papers published within the scope of FEM with AI methodologies. Since its development, the number of publications using the FEM increases every year following an exponential growth. As for AI applications, the complexity of FEM’s applications strongly depends on the computational capacity. Fig.2(a) shows that FEM’s exponential rate becomes even higher from the 1990’s forward. This period coincides with the beginning of massive use of personal computers. At the same period, papers dealing with AI methodologies start to slightly increase. However, at that period, only one AI methodology stands-out, showing a strong growth: the artificial NN technique. Between the 2010-2020 period, almost all AI methodologies show an exponential growth, which is explained by the spread of AI to numerous science fields, from financial to social sciences, from molecular dynamics to urban planning. Fig.2(b) shows the number of papers published per year using the keywords TS-AI-CM, TS-ML-CM, TS-PR-CM, TS-DP-CM and TS-NN-CM. It is visible that NN is the preferred AI methodology in computational mechanics and that the number of papers appears to increase only from 2015 forward. On the other hand, combining AI methodologies with biomechanics is more common. Fig.2(c) shows the number of papers published per year using the keywords TS-AI-B, TS-ML-B, TS-PR-B, TS-DP-B and TS-NN-B. It is visible that until 2010 the number of published papers is very modest, however, since 2010 the number of published papers starts to grow significantly, particularly the ones combining ML and NN with biomechanics. Fig.2(d) shows how the number of published papers per year grow combining AI methodologies with the FEM: TS-AI-FEM, TS-ML-FEM, TS-PR-FEM, TS-DP-FEM and TS-NN-FEM. With Fig.2(d) it is possible to observe a solid growth of NN combined with FEM since the early 1990’s. It is also visible the fast development of FEM applications combined with ML and DL generic methodologies in the last 5 years.

5 Conclusions

This work does not intend to present a survey or a structured review on AI methodologies for CM&B applications. Instead, it intends to introduce the most basic concepts of AI methodology and show the growth potential in CM&B. It were presented the most suited AI methodologies for CM&B applications and how they interact with each other. Therefore, the chief concepts and ideas behind AI for CM&B were disclosed and the rudiments of ML, PR, DL and DL using artificial NN were introduced. Since ML methodologies using general DL techniques and DL by NN are the most popular in CM&B today, these methodologies were presented with a higher detail, allowing to comprehend the high potential of these techniques to enhance significantly the traditional hard computing techniques used in CM&B.

Regarding the large document search performed in the academic database Web of Science, it was found that AI methodologies present a very high growth rate, regardless the application field. The search revealed that ML methodologies using general DL techniques or DL by NN had an exponential growth in the last 10 years, and from the

observed curves it is expected that such trend will continue in the next years. The search also found that AI methodologies combined with computational mechanics is still in its infancy, with very few works published. However, it is possible to observe that the majority of those work were used ML or DL or NN. Regarding AI methodologies combined with biomechanics, it were found more publications, showing an exponential growth in the last 5 years. It is expected that the topic computational mechanics will follow this trend showing the same exponential growth in the next few years. Regarding the use of AI methodologies with FEM, it was found that DL with NN presents a steady growth since the 1990's and that, in the last 5 years, the number of publications on ML-FEM had an exponential growth.

Table 1 – Total number of articles published until July 2020 within the indicated topic/subject (TS) using the combinations of keywords.

AND	"_"	"Computational mechanics" OR "Structural mechanics"	"Biomechanics"	"Finite element method"
"Artificial Intelligence"	TS-AI: 51009 papers	TS-AI-CM: 13 papers	TS-AI-B: 28	TS-AI-FEM: 75 papers
"Machine learning"	TS-ML: 127898 papers	TS-ML-CM: 22 papers	TS-ML-B: 106 papers	TS-ML-FEM: 114 papers
"Deep learning"	TS-DL: 50593 papers	TS-DL-CM: 7 papers	TS-DL-B: 20 papers	TS-DL-FEM: 32 papers
"Pattern recognition"	TS-PR: 67617 papers	TS-PR-CM: 1 papers	TS-PR-B: 39 papers	TS-PR-FEM: 42 papers
"Neural Networks"	TS-NN: 200218 papers	TS-NN-CM: 54 papers	TS-NN-B: 98 papers	TS-NN-FEM: 584 papers

Fig.2 – Number of articles published per year within (a) general topic/subject, (b) computational mechanics/structural mechanics topic/subject, (c) biomechanics topic/subject and (d) finite element method topic/subject.

Some relevant works have been published combining ML with CM&B. The already mentioned surveys from Salehi et al. [1] and Oishi et al. [2] are mandatory. Regarding computational mechanics, very recently, ML methodologies were applied to enhance FEM formulation in several fields, such as creating smart elements [16], improving the numerical integration [2] or combined with fracture mechanics [17]. Regarding computational biomechanics, the literature starts to present some promising works. For instances, in [18,19] the authors present a ML combined with the FEM capable to model the mechanical behaviour of human organs, such as breast tissues and liver, in real-time. Such approach can be used in the near future to support clinical practice and real-time surgeries. Up to now, in CM&B, ML has been combined

mostly with FEM. However, there are several other discretization techniques available in the literature, such particle and meshless methods [20], allowing to achieve higher levels of accuracy and discretization freedom.

This work shows that AI is arriving to CM&B. Its inclusion will allow to accelerate the CM&B analyses and to simulate much more complex multiphysics problems, crossing multiple scales and creating new rules, incomprehensible to human intellectual capacity. A paradigm shift is arriving to CM&B.

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